

Review Article

"G-D's Physics" New "UNCIARE-JRH'S Time-Acceleration" Critical Prediction & International Contest for Validation of 'G-D's Physics' New Twenty-First Century's Paradigm's Further 'Critical Predictions'!

Jehonathan Bentovish

Zefat Academic Colloge, Zefat, Israel

***Corresponding author**

Jehonathan Bentovish (Bentwich), Zefat Academic Colloge, Zefat, Israel

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Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a major "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm underlying (Twentieth Century's) General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New Twenty-First Century's "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, based on direct empirical validations of two (unique) "G-D's Physics" "Critical Predictions" – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR's GRT & QM! Consequently, "G-D's Physics" discovers a (new) "UNCIARE-JRH – AMI Universe's Time-Acceleration" Critical Prediction, which together with three other "Critical Predictions" constitutes the list of (unique) "Critical Predictions" to be tested as part of an "International Contest for Validation of 'G-D's Physics' New Twenty-First Century's Paradigm"! Those (four) "G-D's Physics" "Critical Predictions" include: A) predicted UNCIARE-JRH (precise) "Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc in the rate of the universe's expansion – that will occur on Sep. 23rd-24th, 2025 (relative to the universe's expansion rate prior to Sep. 23rd). B) **Longitudinal Measurement of the (same) UNCIARE-JRH's Cumulative MAI's – that could be measured across a time-span of 10; 50; & 100 years!** C) "UNCIARE-JRH's AMI's Universe's Time Acceleration" Critical Prediction, which predicts that such FTM's (e.g., through "Atomic Optical Clocks") of any Physical System or phenomenon (in the universe) would be "accelerated" in its "temporal value" beginning during the upcoming JRH's (Sep. 23rd-24th, 2025 – i.e., relative to before those two JRH's days)! Consequently, a "modified" (new) "UNCIARE-JRH's AMI Universal Computational Formula" is being presented, which completely unifies (for the first time in Physics) the Four (basic) Physical Features (as well as the Four Forces), and offers an alternative new "Universal Computation/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) (continuously) "originated" physical universe, i.e., with an (altogether) different "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) "Time-Scaling" associated with the JRH's UNCIARE increase in the universe's expansion rate (and an alternative UCP account for "curved Space-Time")!

Note: Dr. Bentovish is now calling all Astronomers, Cosmologists & Experimental Physicists to join the in the world to collaborate with him to further validate the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm. Dr. Bentovish (Bentwich) e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com

Introduction

Twenty-first Century Physics is undergoing a major "Paradigmatic Shift" from the Old (Twentieth Century's) "Material-Causal Random" Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" Twenty-First Century's Physics Paradigm, due to the prior appearance of a basic "Paradigmatic-Crisis" found in the foundations of the Old MCR Paradigm (of GRT & QM); As indicated based on the through analysis of Thomas Kuhn regarding the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions" (1962), the typical "signs" pointing at the emergence of such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" are:

- The appearance of certain "theoretical-inconsistencies" found between the "pillars" of the Old MCR Paradigm. i.e., GRT & QM!
- A principle inability of the Old MCR Paradigm to explain a major empirical phenomenon, i.e., the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion – assumed to be "caused" by a purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" concept (assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the matter in the universe), but which could not be detected experimentally for the past two full decades (despite intensive efforts to do so)?!

According to Kuhn's (thorough) analysis, following the appearance of

such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" (within any given scientific discipline), there emerges a "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP): i.e., "G-D's Physics" which – if shown capable of resolving these two (a & b) elements of the "Paradigmatic Crisis", and in addition is capable of:

- Identifying at least one (unique) "Critical Prediction" of this NSP "G-D's Physics" (candidate) that is significantly different from the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR Paradigm;
- To the extent that this (unique) "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm can be empirically validated as more accurate than the corresponding prediction/s of the Old MCR's GRT or QM; and given the satisfaction of all the preceding (a-c) criteria, then this New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm must be accepted as the New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) for Twenty-First Century Physics! [1-26].

Methods & Results

In order to directly contrast between the new "G-D'S PHYSICS" Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-D'S PHYSICS" identified two unique "Critical-Prediction" relating to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in Its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) due to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" (CHCFH) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hasha-

nah" (New Year's) time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCP; According to the Old ("Material-Causal") GRT's Paradigm, the (purely hypothetical concept of) DM predicts a "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion – i.e., which should not increase over time! In contrast, according to one of the new Theoretical Postulates of the "G-D's PHYSICS" termed: The "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" (CHCFH), whenever there is a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF), e.g., of a large group of human-beings focusing upon this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), this results in an "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" ("UNCIARE")! For example, during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana's" (new year) two days' special time-interval, according to the CUFT (unique) "UNCIARE-JRH" "Critical Prediction", there should be measured a "non-continuous increase" in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., predicted to occur during the JRH's two days special annual interval of a CHCF!)

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction

Pohl et al.[27-29] set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x, o-y, o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i \dots n\{o-x, o-y, o-z\} \{UF(i \dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x, o-y, o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Confirmation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction

In order to confirm "G-D's Physics" (unique) "UNCIARE (JRH)" Critical Prediction it is necessary to gauge and compare the rate of the universe's expansion – at its early (Cosmological) stages, as opposed to the current (Astronomical) measure of the universe's rate of expansion: Once again, according to "G-D's Physics" (unique) UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction, the rate of the universe's expansion increases at every year's JRH's CHCF (two days' special time interval – e.g., at which Millions of Jew collectively focus on this singular higher-ordered UCP!), hence predicted to lead to an overall increase in the rate of the universe's expansion from its early Cosmological measure to the current Astronomical measure of the universe's expansion rate! (As indicated above, this unique "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction predicting an overall increase in the universe's expansion rate from its early Cosmological to the current Astronomical rate of expansion – stands in stark contrast to the Old MCR's

GRT's purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" prediction regarding the rate of the universe's expansion which should remain **constant over time!?**)

Indeed, the "Hubble's Tension"[34] empirical findings (unequivocally) supports "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH prediction regarding such an increase in the rate of the universe's expansion – from the universe's initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion [34-40]?! In other words, "G-D's Physics" unique UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction, predicting that the Universe's expansion rate will increase (annually) during every consecutive JRH's two days' (special) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – is validated by the "Hubble's Tension"[34-40], findings! In contrast, these "Hubble's Tension"[34-40] findings cannot be explained by the current "Standard Material-Causal" Paradigm of GRT, which assumes that the universe's accelerated expansion is the result of (purely hypothetical) "Dark Matter" concepts, which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe (but which failed to be detected despite twenty years of intensive experimentation attempting to do so)!? Even beyond that, even theoretically this (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" concept could not account for the empirically observed "Hubble's Tension"34-40 because such a (purely hypothetical) DM concept could only account for a constant-rate expansion of the universe (e.g., over time), but not for the "Hubble's Tension"[32-34-40], results indicating that the universe's rate of expansion increases over time, which precisely confirm "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction!

Likewise, the empirically measured "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings precisely support "G-D's Physics" novel UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given particle as function of its "Object Spatial Consistency" (across a series of UF's Frames); therefore the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the (relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen") than the (relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen") was predicted by "G-D's Physics" to lead to a "spatially-smaller"- and spatially more accurate"- measurement of that "Muon-Hydrogen" empirical findings! In contrast, these "Proton-Radius Puzzle" empirical findings could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force" [49], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction[53,57], higher dimension gravity [48], a new boson [52], and the quasi-free hypothesis π^{*51} ; and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm! Hence, these "Proton-Radius Puzzle" empirical results unequivocally support "G-D's Physics" unique Critical Prediction stemming from its (novel) UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given (subatomic) particle (or relativistic object)!

Discussion

Based upon the (abovementioned) empirical validation of two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "MCR's" GRT & QM, we must accept "G-D's Physics" as the New (satisfactory) Scientific Paradigm (NSP) for Twenty-First Century Physics!

This (unequivocal) acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the NSP for Twenty-First Century's Physics Paradigm stems – not only from its more accurate (unique differential) "Critical Predictions" (e.g., than the corresponding GRT's & QM's predictions); but also based on its satisfaction of Thomas Kuhn's (abovementioned) stringent scientific criteria necessary for the acceptance of any such NSP as more valid than the "Old Standard Paradigm" (e.g., MCR Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM:

A. "G-D's Physics" Resolves GRT-QM "Theoretical Inconsistency":

The principle "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM stems from

GRT's insistence upon the "Speed of Light Barrier", i.e., the basic postulate that nothing (in the universe) can travel at a speed greater than the Speed of Light! Therefore, the empirically validated "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon: wherein a certain subatomic measurement of one (of two) "entangled-particles" – "instantaneously" affects (and "determines") the "complimentary-value" of the other "entangled particle" (which may be separated by a distance greater than can be traversed by the Speed of Light emanating from that "first measured entangled particle"!)) seems to violate the "Speed of Light Barrier" (SOLB) of GRT!?

The manner in which "G-D's Physics" New Twenty-First Century's Paradigm is able to resolve this (apparent) GRT-QM "theoretical-inconsistency" is based on its (breakthrough) discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' Four (basic) Physical Features (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") for every consecutive "Universal Frame/s" (i.e., comprising the whole entire physical universe at every "minimal-time point"*) at the incredible rate* of "c2/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec! Indeed, according to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, the UCP possesses two (out of three) specific "Computational Dimensions". i.e., "Framework" – each comprising two possible levels: Framework (e.g., "frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent"), producing four possible "combinations" corresponding to those Four Physical Features:

UCP's "Frame-consistent" computation: "Space"

The UCP's computation of "Frame-consistent" values for each exhaustive spatial pixel yields the "space" value for each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)!

"Space"

S: $(f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$ such that: $f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] \leq f_{\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}[UF's(i\dots n)]$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

UCP's "Frame-inconsistent" computation: "Energy"

The UCP's computation of "Frame-inconsistent" values for each exhaustive spatial pixel yields the "energy" value for each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)!

"Energy"

E: $(f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$

such that: $f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] > f_{\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}[UF's(i\dots n)]$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

UCP's "Object-consistent" computation: "Mass"

The UCP's computation of "Frame-inconsistent" values for each exhaustive spatial pixel yields the "energy" value for each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)!

"Mass"

M: $[O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its com-

putation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

UCP's "Object-inconsistent" computation: "Time"

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

T: $\sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}}[UF(n)] \neq O_{i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}}\{UF(i\dots n)\}] / c * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$ such that: $T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Table 1 illustrates the UCP's Computational Dimensions' derived Four (basic) Physical Features:

Table 1: UCP's Computational Dimensions' Derivation of the Four Physical Features

Framework/Consist.	Frame	Object
Consistent	"Space"	"Mass"
Inconsistent	"Energy"	"Time"

Based on this (breakthrough) discovery of "G-D's Physics" of that singular higher-ordered UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels' Four basic Physical Features, as: "Framework"- "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"); or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass"), or "inconsistent" ("time") computations; this profound new realization of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm allows for the resolution of the apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT's (strict) SOLB and QM's (empirically validated) "Quantum-Entanglement" phenomenon! This is because once we realize that QM's "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" assumed "complimentary pairs" (e.g., of "space" and "energy" or "mass" and "time") – does not ensue from any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between the subatomic "probe" and "target" elements, but rather from the UCP's "complimentary computation" of either "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") and "inconsistent" ("energy"); or of "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") and ("time") Features; then according to these new "G-D's Physics" UCP's "complimentary computations" (of "space" – "energy"; or "mass" – "time") of the "complimentary-pairs", the abovementioned "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon – is not "caused" by any direct (or even indirect) physical interaction/s between these two "entangled particles"! But is rather brought about (precisely) through this (singular) UCP's complimentary computation of these "UCP's complimentary-pairs"!

Thus, for instance, when that singular (higher-ordered) UCP computes the "complimentary-pairs" of "space" and "energy", e.g., for any such "two entangled particles"; since the UCP's computation of (either of these "entangled particles") "space", (i.e., "Frame-consistent") or "energy", (i.e., "Frame-inconsistent") values are "complimentary", e.g., the more "focus" (or "accuracy") is given to (either of these "entangled particles") "energy"

value – which denotes the UCP's computation of "Object-consistent" value/s, then necessarily also implies that the UCP's "focus" ("or "accuracy" level) for its "complimentary computation" of the "Framework-inconsistent" "energy" value/s (of either of these "complimentary-pairs") must also be affected (in a "complimentary" manner)! Likewise, the UCP's "complimentary computation" of (any of these) "entangled particle's" "Object-consistent" (e.g., "mass") or "Object-inconsistent" ("time") – is also necessarily "complimentary": i.e., the greater "focus" (or "accuracy level") with which the UCP computes any of these "entangled pairs" of either its "Object-consistent" ("mass") or "Object-inconsistent" ("time") value/s, then this also necessarily decreases the "other complimentary pair's" "focus" or "accuracy level"!

In fact, a more comprehensive understanding of the manner in which "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm explicates the true nature of the physical universe – as being continuously "computed", "dissolved", "re-computed" and "developed" (e.g., "simultaneously" for all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe – at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!) portrays the principle difference between the Old "Material-Causal Random" Paradigm's description of either: "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST) of "relativistic objects" or "subatomic particles" – which measures the spatial-temporal value/s of only a "single spatial-temporal point" at any given "time-point"; or of "Multi Spatial-Temporal" (MST) "relativistic gravitational waves" or "QM's (assumed) probability wave-function" (e.g., which is "challenged" by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, as shown previously): which measures (at least) "two (or more) spatial-temporal points" at any given "time-point"; as opposed to "G-D's Physics" "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all "exhaustive spatial points" (in the universe) for every consecutive UF's frame/s!

Table 2: UCP'S "SST", "MST" & "EST" Computations!

UCP's Computations	SST	MST	EST
Num. "ST" Points	1	2+	All Points

B. "G-D's Physics" Explanation for Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion:

Indeed, the acceptance of "G-D's Physics" NSP as the New Twenty-First Century's Physics Paradigm follows from its satisfaction of Kuhn's (second) stringent scientific criterion, e.g., offering an (alternative satisfactory) theoretical explanation for the (otherwise "unexplained") accelerated rate of the universe's expansion rate! (As noted earlier, the Old MCR's "explanation" of the universe's accelerated expansion rate based on GRT's assumed existence of a purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" concept, assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe – but which could not be verified experimentally for the past two full decades, can not be regarded as a "satisfactory" explanation for the universe's empirically observed accelerated expansion rate?!) "G-D's Physics" new alternative explanation for the universe's accelerated rate of expansion stems from its (novel) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, and its (profound) discovery of the UCP's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) Postulate – which has received empirical validation through the (above) "UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction"!

"G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Paradigm

Contrary to the basic "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) assumption of the Old MCR Paradigm, e.g., assuming that any (relativistic or quantum) phenomenon can be explained strictly based on (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between a certain "massive objects" and

their ("caused") "curvature" of "Space-Time" (or between such assumed "curved Space-Time" and its "causal" determination of the "travelling-pathways" of those "massive objects" or of other "less-massive" objects); or of QM's assumed "causal" relationship/s between a certain subatomic "probe" element and its direct "material-causal" physical interaction with another corresponding subatomic "target's probability wave-function" – which "causes" the "collapse" of this (assumed) "probability wave-function" into a singular "complimentary" "energy-mass" or "time-mass" value/s;

"G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm (principally) negates the very possibility of the existence of any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any such relativistic "massive objects" and their (assumed) "curvature of Space-Time", or (conversely) between any such (assumed) "curved Space-Time" and its "causing" (or determination) of the "travelling-pathways" of those "massive objects" or of other "less-massive objects"! Or of the existence of any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between a certain subatomic "probe" element and a corresponding subatomic "target's probability wave-function" which is assumed to "cause" the "collapse" of that "target's probability wave-function" (e.g., into a singular "complimentary": "space-energy" or "mass-time" value/s)!? This is due to "G-D's Physics" discovery of the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels' Four basic Physical Features (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) – which precludes the very possibility of the existence of any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels, e.g., occurring at any single or multiple UF's frame/s! Once we realize, that since that (singular, higher-ordered) UCP "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels for every consecutive UF's frames, therefore there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing any in any (single or multiple) UF's frame/s! Moreover, due to "G-D's Physics" (assumed) complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising the entire physical universe in any single UF's frame/s) "in-between" any two (such) consecutive UF's frame/s (back into the singularity of this UCP!) therefore there cannot also exist any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – across any two ("consecutive" or "non-consecutive" UF's frame/s)!?

Therefore, it has been previously shown that "G-D's Physics" also principally negates GRT's "Big-Bang" Model, which assumes that the universe has been created by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event – which "caused" the creation of all "suns", "galaxies", "mass", "energy" etc.!? This is simply because according to "G-D's Physics" (novel) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, there cannot have existed any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – i.e., including between the (assumed) "Big-Bang" nuclear event and its "causing" (e.g., creation) of any such "suns", "galaxies", "planets", "mass", "energy" etc. ; either in the "first", "second", "third"... "trillionth" etc. UF's frame/s!? Neither could there have been any such "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any such (initially assumed) "Big-Bang" nuclear event and the accelerated expansion of the universe! Nor could there exist any (abovementioned) purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" (DM) concept that is assumed (by the Old MCR Paradigm) to "cause" this accelerated rate of expansion of the universe; e.g., once again, due to the "impossibility" of the existence of any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any such (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" (DM) concept and any "outer galactic elements" (assumed to "cause" their "expulsion" by this purely hypothetical DM!?)

The UCP's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) Postulate

Instead, "G-D's Physics" alternative explanation of the universe's (empirically observed) accelerated rate of expansion is associated with its (novel)

UCP's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Postulate, which postulates that whenever there is a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF), e.g., of a large group of human-beings on this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), then this produces a "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE)! Such as during the two days of the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah" (JRH) in which Millions of Jew (all over the world) singularly focus on this UCP (e.g., CHCF!) – which, in fact, constitutes one (of the two abovementioned) "G-D's Physics" empirically validated (unique) "Critical Predictions"!

As mentioned above, the empirically observed (unexplained) "gap" that exists between the early Cosmological "decreased" measurements of the universe's expansion rate -as opposed to the current "increased" Astronomical accelerated measurements of the universe's rate of expansion (which is termed: "Hubble's Tension") – directly support "G-D's Physics UNCIARE (JRH) unique "Critical Prediction"; but contradicts the Old MCR's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model (e.g., including the purely hypothetical and empirically "unvalidated" "Dark-Matter" concept) that can only account for a "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion!?

We therefore stand at a truly "historic pivotal turning-point" in Twenty-First Century Physics which must necessarily embrace and accept "G-D's Physics" as the New Scientific Paradigm (NSP), e.g., as more valid and more exhaustive than the Old MCR's GRT & QM Models! In fact, as shown previously, this New "G-D's Physics" is not only more valid and accurate than those two (OLD MCR's) GRT & QM Theories, but in fact fully integrates- (and transcends-) both of them within its singular (higher-ordered) more exhaustive discovery of the UCP's "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) that also (fully) unifies (e.g., for the first time in Physics!) between the Four basic "Physical Features" (of "space", "time", energy" and "mass"):

"G-D's Physics" Complete Integration of GRT-QM & the Four Physical Features!

Strikingly, this new alternative ACC "G-D's Physics" theoretical account for the "appearance" of the "Relativistic curvature of Space-Time" by (certain) "massive objects" – which negates the very possibility of the existence of any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions, e.g., between any two (or more Relativistic or Quantum) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing either in the same- or other- UF's frames) "opens the door" for a complete unification between GRT & QM, as well as between GRT's "Gravitational Force" and QM's "Standard Model's" other Three (e.g., Electromagnetic. Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces)! This is simply because "G-D's Physics" the discovery of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP which "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' Four (basic) Physical Features, has also led to its discovery of a singular unified "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) which completely integrates between those Four Physical Features (i.e., as "secondary computational by-products" of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle", "UCP") (Figure 1)!

Figure 1: The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ \text{---} \\ h \end{array} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m} \\
 \text{UF's } \{ \text{א...ה...כ} \} \text{ [Px] } \{ \text{א...ז} \}
 \end{array}$$

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time".

Wherein the UCP represented by the Hebrew Letter "א" computes at an extremely rapid rate, e.g., of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ (sec') simultaneously every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising every consecutive UF's – including the UCP's complete integration of those Four basic Physical Features through the UCF's: s * e / t * m computation (e.g., for each exhaustive spatial pixel – from "a to z")!

In order to see how this (novel) "G-D's Physics" Computational Definitions of each of the Four (basic) Physical Features is (fully) integrated within the UCF's singular formula – i.e., and which also allows for "G-D's Physics" complete integration of GRT & QM (as "special-cases" within the broader- exhaustive- higher-ordered theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" UCF!); let us examine "G-D's Physics" (novel) "Computational Definitions" of each of those Four (basic) Physical Features:

Indeed, "G-D's Physics" (novel) UCP's "Computational Definitions" of the Four Physical Features are based on the discovery of the UCP's two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" ("frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent"): wherein the UCP's computation of the UF's "frame" (level's) – "consistent" (e.g., "space") or "inconsistent" ("energy") Physical Features relates to the UCP's computation of the degree of "consistency" or "inconsistency" of any given "object", relative to the entire UF's ("coordinate-system", e.g., across a series of UF's frame/s)! Or, conversely, the UCP's computation of any given object's "object" (e.g., "internal-composition's) – "consistent" (e.g., "mass") or "inconsistent" (e.g., "time") produce the entire UF's exhaustive spatial pixels' Four basic Physical Features values! (See Table 1).

The UCP's Four Physical Features (Novel) Computational Definitions:

"Space"

S: $(f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$ such that: $f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] \leq f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}[UF's(i..n)]$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i..n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the.

"Energy"

E: $(f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$

such that: $f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}[UF's(i..n)]$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes): $M: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}}[UF(n)] = O_{i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}}\{UF(i..n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$ where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

"Mass"

M: $[O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i..n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"Time"

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

T: $\sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}}[UF(n)] \neq O_{i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}}\{UF(i..n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$ such that: $T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i..n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the

speed of light.

In order to illustrate the (full) integration of "G-D's Physics" singular "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) – not only of the Four (basic) Physical Features, but also of GRT & QM (e.g., as "special-cased" within its UCF, as Einstein envisioned!) let us examine two derivatives of this singular UCF, i.e., of a Relativistic and Quantum Formats!

The UCF's Relativistic Format

$$\left. \begin{matrix} \text{,} \\ \text{E} * \text{s} \\ \text{t} \end{matrix} \right\} = \left. \begin{matrix} \text{M} * \text{c}^2 \\ \text{h} \end{matrix} \right\}$$

in which GRT's (famous) "Energy-Mass Equivalence" is embedded within the UCF.

The UCF's Quantum Format

$$\left. \begin{matrix} \text{,} \\ \text{t} * \text{m} \\ \text{c}^2 \end{matrix} \right\} = \left. \begin{matrix} \text{s} * \text{e} * \text{h} * \\ \text{c}^2 \end{matrix} \right\}$$

in which "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" ("complimentary pairs") are embedded as "special cases" within the UCF (see previously elaborated analysis of "G-D'S PHYSICS").

Interestingly, this (latter) new "G-D's Physics" UCP's (,) computation of the UCF's "Quantum Format" clearly reveals a much "deeper" understanding of the basic "computational constraint" imposed by Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" that stems from "G-D's Physics" singular higher-ordered UCP's simultaneous computation of those Four (basic) Physical Features (for all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe) – rather than as "caused" by any (direct) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two subatomic) "probe" and "target" elements; which serves as the current QM's "theoretical explanation" for Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" (e.g., and associated assumed "collapse" of the "target's probability wave-function" – as "caused" by this direct "material-causal" physical interaction between the subatomic probe and target elements)!? This is because if we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" (novel) UCP's computational definitions of these Four basic Physical Features (above) – arising from the four possible combinations of the two Computational Dimensions: "Framework" ("frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent"): "Frame" – "consistent" (e.g., "space") or "inconsistent" (e.g., "energy"), and "Object" – "consistent" (e.g., "mass") or "inconsistent" ("time")! Then, we can immediately see that the real "intrinsic computational-complimentary" reason for Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" is not any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical

interactions between the subatomic "probe" and "target's" (assumed "probability wave function") elements! But rather, this "UCP's intrinsic computational complementarity" is the real reason for Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" stems from the "UCP's intrinsic computational complementarity": i.e., since the UCP simultaneously computes both the "Framework" – "consistent" ("space") and "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") and "inconsistent" ("time") values of any given object (e.g., exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec'), therefore any increase in the accuracy level of the measurement of any one of these "UCP's computational pairs", i.e., "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") necessarily leads to a proportional decrease in the other "UCP's computational pair's" accuracy level!

Moreover, since this singular (higher-ordered) UCP simultaneously computes all Four Physical Features (for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising each consecutive UF's frame/s), therefore the singular "Universal Computational Formula" completely integrates (e.g., for the first time in Physics!) those Four Physical Features as "secondary computational by-products" of the same singular (higher-ordered) UCP computation! Indeed, as can be seen from the two (abovementioned) "Relativistic" and "Quantum" Formats of this singular UCF, we can see that "G-D's Physics" novel UCF completely integrates – not only between those Four basic Physical Features, but also completely integrates GRT & QM as "special cases" within this broader and (indeed) exhaustive new theoretical framework! Hence, not only do those key Relativistic "Energy-Mass Equivalence" (" $E = Mc^2$ ") and Quantum's Heisenberg's "Uncertainty Principle" (e.g., stemming not from any direct "material-causal" physical interaction between the subatomic "probe" and "target" elements, but is rather due to the "UCP's intrinsic computational complementarity"! being embedded within the singular UCF's Relativistic and Quantum Formats, but more broadly, its been previously shown that all key Relativistic and Quantum phenomena and laws are being replicated (and indeed "transcended" as merely representing "special cases" within "G-D's Physics" more exhaustive theoretical framework).

"G-D's Physics" UCF's Complete Unification of the Four Forces!

Indeed, as shown previously, the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm offers an alternative theoretical explanation for all of Relativistic and Quantum phenomena – solely based on its newly discovered (abovementioned) "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), which simultaneously computes the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" for all exhaustive spatial pixel/c comprising the entire physical universe (of each consecutive UF's frame/s) – as secondary computational by-products of the UCP's singular computation! This also means that the Four (basic) Forces of Nature – i.e., the Weak and Strong Forces, and the Electromagnetic Force, and the Gravitational Force are all solely derived (and produced) by this singular higher-ordered UCP's UCF description of the UCP's simultaneous computation of each of the universe's exhaustive spatial pixels four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – as "Frame's" or "Object's" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computations! This is where (we begin realizing)"G-d's Physic" (abovementioned) UCP's new Computational Definitions for each of these Four Physical Features – also necessarily gives rise- and (in fact) includes- the UCP's computation of the various forms of "energy", i.e., including those specific to each of these "three" Forces: the "Weak", "Strong" and "Electromagnetic" Forces;

"Energy"

$$E: (f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

such that: $f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] > f_{\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}[UF's(i\dots n)]$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate Sys-

tem's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

Likewise, the UCP's (abovementioned novel) Computational Definition of "of "Mass" – i.e., (as shown above) which gives rise to what appears as the "Gravitational Force", as manifesting through the UCP's (abovementioned) "Universal Computational Formula"!

"Mass"

$$M: [O_{\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

As noted above (and previously), the UCP's computation of any type of "energy" is computed by this singular higher-ordered UCP as the degree of "displacement" of any (relativistic or quantum) object relative the coordinates of the entire Universal Frame/s across a series of UF's frames; this means that the "root" for all three "Strong, Weak and Electromagnetic Forces is derived from the UCP's computation of their degree of "displacement" across a given series of UF's frames! Moreover, based on the complete integration of those four basic physical features comprising any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe through the UCP's Universal Computational Formula (UCF), therefore the entire array of subatomic particles described by the Standard Model – amongst which those Three Nuclear Forces operate are exhaustively described by the UCP's UCF! Indeed, the multifarious different levels of electromagnetic charge, mass, energy values etc. of each of these particular Standard Model particles and components manifests as one of the specific configurations- and relationships- described by the UCP's newly discovered UCF! In other words, the Three Strong, Weak, Electromagnetic Forces describe different levels and configurations of the UCP's singular higher-ordered UCP's computation of the degree of any given particle (object) "displacement" across a given series of UF's frames! In that sense, there is no real "difference" between the UCP's computation of the degree of "displacement" of the Strong, Weak or Electromagnetic Forces operating within the nucleus or between the nucleus and its surrounding particles or between particles and other elements; In fact, the whole theoretical conceptualization of the very computational definitions of each of these multifarious Standard Model particles – including their "mass", "energy", "localization" and "temporal" values is viewed (for the first time) as one singular fully integrated computation by the UCP, rather than existing as "separate" and "independent" particles operating by different (Three) Strong, Weak or Electromagnetic Forces...

No longer are the various Standard Model particles viewed as "independent" entities, nor do the Three Forces operating between them or uniting them seem as "separate" or "independent"; rather, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm's discovery of the singular higher ordered "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) completely unifies all of these apparently different subatomic particles and the Three Forces governing them as manifestations of different possible relationships described by this singular higher-ordered UCP UCF! Indeed, it is suggested that just as the discovery of the "Periodic Table" provided a "blue-print" for the basic constitution of all possible chemical elements in Nature, just as Watson, & Crick discovery of the basic constituent elements of the DNA gave Science its basic understanding of the basic "building-blocks" of all Genetic-Biological organisms (and functions); so does "G-d's Physics" 21st Century Physics Paradigm's discovery of the new "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) provides Theoretical Physics (and Science more generally) the basic understanding of all of Nature's basic (possible) "plethora" of subatomic particles and Four basic Forces, i.e., the Strong & Weak Forces, the Electromagnetic Force and the Gravitational Force! It is suggested that by using this newly discovered UCF we can find and identify all of the known "Standard Model" par-

ticles – and potentially additional "prospective]" (i.e., yet to be discovered!) e.g., based upon the precise interrelationships between any given particle's "mass", "energy", "spatial" and "temporal" values (see below)! Hence, this new UCF also integrates and unifies between the Three (Strong, Weak and Electromagnetic) Nuclear Forces (of the Standard Model and Quantum Mechanics) and the Gravitational Force (of General Relativity Theory) – simply because the Gravitational Force, alike these other Three Forces is computed by the singular higher-ordered UCF! As noted above, "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm offers a completely new and different theoretical account for General Relativity's "Gravitational Force", as well as for the Three Nuclear Forces, e.g., as stemming from the UCP's UCF computation of the four integrated and complimentary physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – not as being "caused" by certain "massive objects" "curving" "Space-Time", but rather as being produced by the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe; Specifically, what "appears" as General Relativity's "Gravitational Force" is the result of the UCP's computation of certain "regions" of each consecutive UF's frame/s to be comprised of "High-Mass; Low Energy" (HMLE) regions which are therefore computed as "spatially-consistent" regions which remain relatively "constant" across a given series of UF's frames, as opposed to other regions constituting these series of UF's frames which may be defined as constituting "Low-Mass; High Energy" ("LMHE") regions which therefore do not appear as "spatially-consistent" across a series of UF's frames! This differential UCP's computation of those HMLE vs. LMHE regions (according to "G-d's Physics" New Computational Definition of "Mass") creates an appearance of the "curvature" of "Space-Time" around certain "massive objects"?!

In much the same manner, "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm also offers an alternative new theoretical account for these "Three Forces" – not as being "caused" by any direct (or indirect) physical interactions between any of the "Standard Model" list of existing particles; but rather as being produced by the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), thereby producing those "apparent" subatomic particle's associated "Three Forces"! It is perhaps important to highlight the unique new (expansive, higher-ordered) perspective offered by "G-D's Physics" New 21st Century Paradigm – shedding a complete new light upon the complete unification of the Four basic Forces based on the operation of the singular, higher-ordered UCP; First (as we've already seen), due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s, and the discovery of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) Paradigm– then this "G-D's Physics" (novel) ACC Scientific Paradigm (principally) negates the very possibility of the existence of any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frames! This implies that there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any of the subatomic elementary particles that are currently assumed to "transfer" the effects of Three (out of four) Forces – the Weak, Strong and Electromagnetic! As noted previously, this principle negation of the existence of any direct (or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two or more particle/s (or exhaustive spatial pixels) is most apparent when we take into consideration the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe (e.g., and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels and subatomic particles) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s – which negates the very possibility of the existence of any such physical interactions or effects transferred across any two consecutive or non-consecutive UF's frames! Hence, the basic "material-causal" assumption underlying Relativity's explanation of the curvature of Space-Time as "caused" by its direct physical interaction with certain "massive objects" (as evinced in Einstein's Equations), as well as underlying the current "material-causal" Quantum, Standard Model explanation of the other (three) Forces – Strong, Weak and Electromagnetic as being "carried by" certain elementary particles being

transferred between particles is strictly negated by the New "G-d's Physics A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! Instead, based on "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's discovery (and description) of the manner in which the singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) – e.g., through the UCP's "Universal Computational Formula" (and based on the UCP's new computational definitions of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" associated with two of its Computational Dimensions) offers an entirely new (and fascinating) way of viewing each of these Four Forces as arising from simultaneous and integrated computation of this singular higher-ordered UCP! In other words, the manner in which "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm unifies between the "Three Forces" and the "Gravitational Force" is based on its discovery of the singular higher-ordered UCP's simultaneous computation of all of the physical universe's exhaustive spatial pixels based on its unitary "Universal Computational Formula" (UCP) which completely unified between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time"; According to this New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm theoretical framework, both the "Gravitational Force" and the "Three (other) Forces" represent "apparent, phenomenal and transient Forces" which are computed together by the UCP's UCF for each of the universe's consecutive UF's frames!

"The UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table"!

Another important facet of "G-D's Physics" complete integration of both GRT & QM – as "special cases" within the broader theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) can be glanced from "G-D's Physics" "Critical Prediction" of the existence of a ("prospective") "The UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table", which will be derived from the different possible computational relationships for each of the "known" Standard Model's subatomic particles, as well as the expected discovery of multiple prospective subatomic particles that can be derived from the specific stipulated computational relationships between the UCF's Four basic Physical Features, e.g., and their associated (abovementioned) Computational Definitions;

The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ \hline h \end{array} \right\} = \underline{s * e}$$

UF's {n...n...x} [Px] (a...z) t * m

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time".

"Energy"

$$E: (f_i\{x,y,z\}[UF(i)] - \dots f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

$$\text{such that: } f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)] > f_i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\} [UF's(i..n)]$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based

on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

"Mass"

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

$$M: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} \{UF(n)\}] = O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$
 where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" $\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}$ values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

$$M: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"Time"

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" $\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}$ values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} \{UF(n)\}] \neq O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} \{UF(i\dots n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$
 such that: $T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Specifically, it is predicted that every existent (e.g., already discovered) or "prospective" (e.g., to be discovered) subatomic particle would conform to the UCF's stipulated computational relationships between the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – alongside the above outlined computational definitions of each of these four physical features! In this manner, this novel major discovery made by "G-d's Physics" New "UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table" may be (somewhat) likened to the "historic discovery" of the Chemical "Periodic-Table" which explicated the mutual basis- and atomic values constraints- imposed based on the realization that the difference between the various elements (e.g., also pertaining to the then known chemical elements, as well as to the then "unknown prospective" elements that were verified based on this stipulated "Periodic-Table", subsequently); This is because "G-d's Physics" discovery of this novel "UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table" also reveals the basic underlying UCP's computational "mechanism" and "constraints" for all (already) discovered and "prospective" (to be discovered) elementary particles, i.e., as constrained by the UCP's UCF's basic stipulated relationships between the four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"), and their accompanying UCP's computational definitions!

Indeed, to the extent that prospective validations of this "G-D's Physics" Predicted "UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table" will be empirically validated (i.e., of even a single "existent" or "prospective" subatomic particle) which conforms to the UCF's computational relationships between the Four basic Physical Features, then this will unequivocally support "G-D's Physics" as being capable of offering an alternative computational approach to the Standard Model – i.e., which replicates all of the Standard Model's known particle's physical properties, but offers a higher-ordered broader (and exhaustive) novel "A-Causal Computational" (ACC) theoretical framework describing QM's Standard Model as a "special-case" within "G-D's Physics" UCF (e.g., that fully integrates both GRT & QM as integral parts of this singular higher-ordered UCF)!

G-D's Physics' Novell Computational Definition of the "Gravitational Force" Metamorphosizes "Space-Time" Curvature!

Instead, G-D's Physics' New ACC Scientific Paradigm explains GRT's "Gravitational Force" – not as "caused" by (certain) "massive objects" causing the "curvature of space-time" (i.e., which is negated by "G-D's Physics" new ACC Paradigm, as explained above); but rather through "G-D's Physics" (novel) UCP's computational definition of "Mass" (e.g., of any given subatomic particle or of any relativistic object) – as the degree of "Object-Consistent" presentations of any such "object" across a given series of UF's frames!

"Mass"

$$M: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

Surprisingly, this novel UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given (subatomic particle or relativistic) "object" offers an entirely new understanding of the "curvature of Space-Time", as well as of the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; which when taken together with the (simultaneous) UCP's computation of the other three Physical Features (for every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe!) allows "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm to completely unify (for the first time in Physics!) between those Four basic Physical Features, as well as between GRT & QM! Indeed, according to The New "G-D's Physics" UCF's simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic Physical Features creates (relatively) "consistent regions" (i.e., within a given "location" in the "coordinates" of the "Universal Frame" – across a series of UF's frames!): which may be characterizes as "High-Mass; Low Energy" ("HMLE") "consistent regions, represented by the large "red" circles (in Figure 1); As opposed to other "Low-Mass; High-Energy" (LMHE) which appear as (relatively) "inconsistent-regions" (e.g., within a given "location" in the "coordinates" of the Universal Frame – across a series of UF's frames!); Hence, as we can see (in Figure 1) the UCP's computation of "differential consistency regions": a) The "HMLE" "consistent regions" of the "large Red circles", which remain "spatially-consistent" across the two UF's frames; as opposed to : b) The "LMHE" "inconsistent regions" of the "small (alternating) blue/white" which continuously "alternate" (i.e., are "spatially inconsistent") across the two illustrated UF's frames! This implies that those LMHE (alternating "blue/white circles") create a "vacuum" or an "empty-alternating space" around those "consistent" HMLE ("Red circle), thereby giving rise to the "appearance" of "curved Space-Time" around those HMLE "consistent Red circles"!

Figure 2: "G-D's Physics" Alternative Explanation for "Curved Space-Time"!

However, the great "elegance" of this New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (e.g., empirically proven to be more valid e.g., in two of its unique "Critical-Predictions" than the corresponding predictions of the Old "MCR": GRT & QM Paradigm); is that its novel computational definition of the UCP's computation of the "mass" value of any given (relativistic or quantum) "object" allows it to derive an altogether new alternative explanation for the apparent "curvature of Space-Time" by (certain) "massive" objects! Since (as mentioned above and previously), according to the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single (or even multiple) UF's (e.g., due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!); therefore this New ACC "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is shown capable of deriving an "appearance" of those "HMLE" (e.g., "large Red circle") "consistent regions" remaining relatively "stable" across a series of UF's frame/s, as opposed to the "inconsistent regions" of those "LMHE" (e.g., alternating "blue/white small circles") which produces a "vacuum" or "empty-space" around those "HMLE -consistent regions", thereby giving rise to the appearance of a "curved Space-Time" around those "HMLE" ("Red circle")!

"G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Precise & Longitudinal Measurements!

Based upon "G-D's Physics" discovery of that singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) of the entire physical universe (e.g., at every "minimal time-point" at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!") Another (novel) Theoretical Postulate of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) which stipulates that whenever there exists a large group of individual human-beings such as during the two days of the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah" (JRH) in which Millions of Jews (all around the world) focus on the singularity of this "UCP", then this brings about an "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in Its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) – which can explain the (otherwise) "unexplained" gap that exists between the early Cosmological value of the universe's rate of

expansion and the current (significantly increased) Astronomical rate of the universe's expansion, i.e., recently termed: the "Hubble's Tension"!

Hence, "G-D's Physics" alternative theoretical explanation for the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion is given through G-D's Physics "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Expansion" (UNCIARE), e.g., brought about by a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF), such as during the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah's" (JRH) two days special time-interval in which Millions of Jews (all over the world) focus upon this singular (higher-ordered) UCP! Hence, the accelerated expansion of the universe's expansion rate is brought about by the JRH-CHCF, which results in a predicted "UNCIARE-JRH" annual increase in the universe's expansion rate! (e.g., rather than is the result of the "purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" [DM] concept – i.e., which is in fact negated by G-D's Physics' NSP: a) because this purely hypothetical DM concept failed to be verified experimentally for the past two full decades?! And b) due to "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Computational Duality Principle" [CDP] which principally negates its existence, based on a computational-empirical analysis! see below). This UNCIARE-JRH annual increase in the universe's expansion rate has been calculated to comprise a "*Minimal Annual Increase" (MAI) of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ per year; This (novel) G-D's Physics unique "Critical Prediction" of the UNCIARE-JRH's increase of an MAI (e.g., annually) opens an entirely new "window of opportunity" for the validation of the G-D's Physics NSP – as more valid than the Old MCR Paradigm (e.g., of GRT & QM), i.e., both through: a) "Precise" MAI (sensitive) annual Astronomical measurements "during" the JRH's two days' special time-interval; B) Based on "Longitudinal" Astronomical/Cosmological measurements indicating a "cumulative" increase in the universe's expansion rate over any given "time-interval" (e.g., such as over the past 10, 50 or 100 years, or potentially much longer time-intervals, etc., as delineated below)!

Specifically, the significant increase in the universe's measured rate of expansion, i.e., from its (initial) Cosmological "Background Radiation" rate to its (current) "Astronomical" (significantly higher) rate of expansion – termed the "Hubble's Tension"[31-39], precisely supports G-D's Physics' assumed "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in Its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE-JRH) "Critical Prediction", as more valid than the Old MCR's (GRT's) "constant-expansion rate" corresponding prediction (see Figure 3):

Figure 3: G-D's Phys. UNCIARE & Univ. Age!

This is because, according to Old MCR's Paradigm's GRT "Big-Bang" Model, the universe's expansion rate should be "constant" – as caused by the assumed initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event (e.g., and two additional "Exceptional Expansive Events" (or factors, EEE's; as delineated below and previously). Specifically, the (purely hypothetical) "Dark Matter" [DM] concept, which is assumed by the Old MCR Paradigm to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe (e.g., but which could not be detected experimentally for the past two decades despite numerous attempts to do so?!) – could only account for such a "constant rate" of the universe's expansion, because the quantity of this purely hypothetical DM is (itself) "constant" (e.g., or may in fact "diminish" over time, hence leading to a deceleration of the universe's expansion rate...) Hence, according to the Old MCR's GRT Model of the universe, the universe has been created 13.8 Billion years ago, and since then its expansion rate should have been "constant" (i.e., as further delineated below through this MCR's assumed three purely hypothetical EEE's). In contrast, according to the G-D's Physics (novel) Scientific Paradigm, there exists a "Universe's non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE), which is brought about through the JRH's (two days') "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) upon the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which increases the universe's rate of expansion by a Minute Annual Increase (MAI) (i.e., of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc (during the JRH's two days' time-interval!) Hence, the existence of this (specific JRH associated) CHCF is seen as "critical" for the continuous (cumulative) increase in the universe's "accelerated" expansion rate, which also points at the G-D's Physics "Six Days Creation Model" (delineated previously) highlighting the centrality of this CHCF as a key (essential and necessary) factor for the empirically observed "UNCIARE" (e.g., otherwise "unexplained") increase in the universe's expansion rate! Consequently, the G-D'S PHYSICS introduces an entirely different account of the universe's (stipulated) age (and "origin") of the physical universe, e.g.,

to be derived from the MAI's predicted (annual increase) in the universe's expansion rate: originated 5785 years ago!

Therefore, the current article provides initial (unequivocal) empirical support for the G-D's Physics UNCIARE's (unique) "Critical Prediction" regarding the (cumulative) MAI's increase in the universe's expansion rate – i.e., producing the otherwise ("unexplained") "Hubble's Tension"! This is (once again) because unlike GRT's "Big-Bang" Model which assumes a "constant" rate of the universe's expansion (e.g., and the universe's creation based on an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event dated 13.8 Billion years ago) – leading to an "unexplained" "Hubble's Tension" Enigma which cannot account for a significant increase in the universe's expansion rate over time; the (novel) G-D'S PHYSICS explains the universe's (continuous) "origination" by that (singular, higher-ordered) UCP, based on its continuous computation- "dissolution"- "re-computation" and "evolution"- of every exhaustive spatial pixel (e.g., simultaneously), at an incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec! thereby leading to the UCP's production of an incredibly rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every such "minimal time-point"! Indeed, according to this (entirely new) conception of the universe's (constant and continuous) "origination"- "dissolution"- "re-computation"- and "development"- by this singular (higher-ordered) UCP; and the (abovementioned) centrality of the human CHCF (e.g., during the JRH's two days' special time-interval), which brings about an annual "MAI" increase in the UCP's rate of the universe's expansion rate – leads to the G-D's Physics (clear and unique) "Critical Prediction" of "UNCIARE", which is empirically validated- by the (otherwise "unexplained" by the Old MCR's GRT "Big-Bang Model"! Indeed, it is due to the G-D's Physics centrality of the JRH (two days') CHCF (time-interval) – and specifically the MAI's (cumulative) increase in the universe's expansion rate (over time), that the G-D's Physics stipulated age of the physical universe is only 5785 (rather than the Big-Bang Model's

stipulated 13.8 Billion years!

In order to further support this (novel) G-D's Physics UCP's CHCF (JRH's) model of the universe's UNCIARE increase (over time), we highlight its (conceptual computational) negation of the Old MCR's Big-Bang Model of a "constantly" expanding universe: According to the Old MCR Paradigm's GRT "Big-Bang" Model, the universe's current rate of expansion can be explained based on three "Exceptional Expansive Events" (or factors, EEE's): 1) Initial "Big-Bang" Event: the creation of the entire physical universe based on an initial nuclear event. 2) Cosmological Factor: exceptional ("unexplained") anti-gravitational effect that is causing the universe's constant-rate increase in its expansion rate. 3) Purely hypothetical ("unexplained") "Dark-Matter" Concept: that is assumed (somehow) to "cause" an increase in the universe's expansion!?! However, even beyond the (perplexing) failure of Astronomers to experimentally detect the actual existence of this (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" concept (for the past twenty years!?) even from a theoretical standpoint, this (purely hypothetical) Dark Matter (DM) concept – could not account for an increase in the universe's expansion rate!?! This is because even if there existed such a (purely hypothetical) DM concept (or element) – assumed to (somehow) "push" the outer-galactic elements in the universe, it could only do so at a "constant-rate", e.g., because it's quantity cannot increase over time! This means that over time, the rate of the universe's expansion could only remain constant – or (much more likely) decrease!

In fact, the very (computational) structure of GRT's (three) "Exceptional Expansive Effects" (EEE's), e.g., (1) "Big-Bang" event; (2) "Cosmological Factor"; (3) "Dark-Matter" – all share two (very important) characteristics:
a) These three EEE's are based on the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm's basic "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) structure; which has been shown by the G-D's Physics "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) to be "computationally flawed", i.e., lead to an inevitable "logical-inconsistency" and (ensuing) "computationally-indeterminacy", and are therefore negated by the CDP (as "invalid")!
b) These three EEE's can only account for a "constant rate" of the universe's expansion (e.g., or more likely a "decreasing rate" of the universe's expansion) "over time" – but cannot account for an "increased rate" of the universe's expansion over time!?

Indeed, when we examine each of these three EEE's (e.g., individually), we can see that none of them can account for an "increasing rate" of the universe's expansion: a) The "Big-Bang" (initial) nuclear event cannot account for an increasing rate of the universe's expansion, since the initial "impetus" of the Big-Bang's nuclear explosion necessarily pushes the universe's outer galactic elements at a certain "constant" rate, (e.g., or more likely will decrease over time) but will not "increase" over time! b) The "Cosmological Constant" – despite it being "unexplainable": e.g., there is no "etiological" physical explanation for its repulsive effect, or the nature of such an effect; in any event such an "axiomatic repulsive effect" must also be "constant"! This is due to the fact that this "Cosmological Constant" has been defined as "constant"! c) "Dark-Matter" (DM): this purely hypothetical DM – despite the fact that it could not be detected experimentally (for the past twenty years, despite numerous attempts to do so!?) could only "push" those outer galactic regions in a "constant" (e.g., or more likely a "decreasing" rate) over time; this i.e., because, once again, unless this "DM" could somehow "increase in quantity" (over time), its effect could not "increase" over time!

Indeed, an examination of the SRCS Computational Structure of each of these three EEE's has revealed that they all share the same basic SRCS' (intrinsic) "computational flaw", which is exposed through the CDP – and points at the inevitable existence of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP), which according to the G-D'S PHYSICS (simultaneously) computes all exhaustive spatial points in the universe

Paradigm at the "unfathomable" rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ (sec)!)

The "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) Negation of the GRT's SRNCS Structure!

According to G-D's Physics' "Computational Duality Principle" Postulate, the basic "Computational Structure" of GRT's Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., termed: a "Self-Referential Negative Computational System" (SRNCS) is "computationally flawed", i.e., it inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" – which are contradicted by GRT's Computational System's proven empirical capacity to determine the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion, thereby pointing at the singular higher-ordered UCP that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe! Specifically, the GRT's SRNCS Computational Structure assumes that it is solely based on the direct physical interactions (di) between GRT's basic "Curved Space-Time" (due to the presence of certain "massive-objects") "Contractive-Stable Universe" [C-STMo : CSU], e.g., describing a universe that is fundamentally "contracting" or being "stable" (i.e., "constant"); and the three (abovementioned) EEE's "expulsive-effects", e.g.: BB, CC, and DE – all describing a (constant) "accelerated-expansion" of the universe produces such a SRNCS Computational Structure:
GRT's SRNCS:

PR{[C-STMo : CSU], [EEE-BB, CC, DE/DM]} → "Not C-STMo : CSU" / di ?!

Wherein it is assumed that GRT's fundamentally assumed "Contractive-Stable Universe" (e.g., due to the curvature of Space-Time by certain "massive objects") : [C-STMo : CSU] seems to both "exist" and "Not exist" at the same "di" computational level, e.g., constituting a basic "logical-inconsistency" and associated "computational indeterminacy" implying an (apparent) inability of such a SRNCS System to determine the "existence" or "non-existence" of this {[C-STMo : CSU]}! But, since empirically the universe is in fact expanding (at an accelerated rate!), e.g., "Not {[C-STMo : CSU]}"; therefore, according to the CDP there must exist a singular higher-ordered UCP that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each UF's at the rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ sec")!

Conclusion

The Current article presents a novel "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm whose need arises from the fundamental "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM), represented by: a) an apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between these two basic "pillars" of this Old MCR Paradigm. b) A principle inability of the Old MCR Paradigm to explain a key "unexplained (major) empirical phenomenon", i.e., the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion which is assumed to be "explained" by purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" concept (which is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe, but which could not be detected experimentally for the past two full decades despite numerous attempts to do so!?) In contrast, the novelty of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) Scientific Paradigm stems from its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at the (incredible) rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ sec"(!) which was shown capable of resolving this apparent GRT-QM "theoretical-inconsistency", e.g., through its exhaustive incorporation of both "Single Spatial Temporal" (SST) Relativistic, and "Multi Spatial-Temporal" (MST) Quantum sorts of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP computations – which are (both) embedded within the UCP's "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" (EST) computation (i.e., of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe at every such "minimal time-point": $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ sec!) Indeed, this EST (novel) computation of the

UCP has led not only to the complete unification of GRT & QM – but also (for the first time in Physics) between the Four (basic) Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") as well as the Four Forces, based on "G-D's Physics" discovery of a (novel) "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF):

The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{array} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

UF's {n...n...x} [Px| (a...z)]

That is accompanied with the (novel) "UCP's Computational Definitions" for those four basic Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time").

The significance of this work is that it not only is shown capable of resolving the basic GRT-QM "theoretical-inconsistency", and offers an alternative (satisfactory) explanation for the (otherwise "unexplained") "Hubble's-Tension", i.e., the (unexplained) gap that exists between the current Astronomical (increased) rate of the universe's expansion, relative to "early-universe" Cosmological (decreased) rate of the universe's expansion rate; Based on "G-D's Physics" postulate of the existence of a "Universe's Non-Continuous Increased Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) that is associated with such (special) time-intervals in which there exists a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF), e.g., in which Millions of human-beings (collectively) focus on that singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) – such as during the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah's" (JRH's) two days (special) time interval (in which Millions of Jews all focus on this singular UCP!); which is predicted to bring about such a UNCIARE-JRH (significant) increase in the universe's rate of expansion (for the entire subsequent Jewish Year)!

Most significantly, the current article identified two (unique) "Critical Predictions" differentiating "G-D's Physics" predictions from the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR: GRT's & QM's predictions; with one of these two (unique) predictions being this UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction – which received empirical support stemming from "G-D's Physics" "Non-Continuous Increase" predicted increase in the rate of the universe's expansion that can resolve the (otherwise "unexplained") "Hubble's Tension" phenomenon! (In contrast to the principle inability of the Old MCR's GRT "constant-rate" of expansion prediction - of the "purely hypothetical" & "empirically-unverified" "Dark-Matter" concept!?) Indeed, this "surprising" capacity of "G-D's Physics" New ACC Scientific Paradigm to not only resolve the principle "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM (and unify for the first time between the Four Physical Features and also between the Four Forces based on its discovery of the UCF!); When supported empirically by two of its (unique) "Critical Predictions", including its UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction – which was also shown to resolve the (otherwise "unresolved" key) "Hubble's-Tension" positions "G-D's Physics" as a (serious candidate) for Physics New Scientific Para-

digm (NSP).

A. G-D's Physics Predicts an "UNCIARE-JRH's Acceleration of Time" Critical Prediction!

Based upon the above results indicating that the resolution of the "Hubble's Tension" Enigma – can only be satisfactorily explained through "G-D's Physics" breakthrough new "Time-Scaling" of the universe, i.e., based on the centrality of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) and the UNCIARE's annual increase in the rate of the universe's expansion; it becomes clear that there exists an increase in the rate of the UCP's computation of the extremely rapid series of UF's frame/s! In other words, the manner in which "G-D's Physics" New ACC Scientific Paradigm explains the otherwise "unexplained" "Hubble's Tension" Enigma - e.g., which could not be explained through the purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" concept that is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe but could not be detected experimentally (despite two full decades of intensive experimentations attempting to do so!?) And moreover, is negated based on the "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion – predicted by such "purely hypothetical" "Dark-Matter" concept, which is contradicted by the "Hubble's Tension" empirical measurements of the clear increase in the universe's expansion rate from its "early Cosmological" rate to the contemporary increased "Astronomical" rate?! The manner in which "G-D's Physics" New (empirically validated) ACC Paradigm can explain this "Hubble's Tension" explicated "UNCIARE-JRH" annual increase in the universe's expansion rate has to do with the UCP's increase in its rate of computation of the UF's series – which increases its basic rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec' by the stipulated AMI increase of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc! This means that the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) at the Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH) which brings about the UCP's UNCIARE-JRH's increase of an Annual Minimal Increase (AMI) – yields such an AMI increase – manifesting both in the "macroscopic-relativistic" rate of the universe's expansion rate (e.g., relating to the "spatial" increase in the outer-regions of the universe), as well as in the "microscopic-quantum" measure of the acceleration of "time", i.e., throughout the universe; (As well as to the other two (basic) Physical Features, e.g., of "mass" and "energy" – since this annual increase in the UCP's AMI's rate of production of the (extremely rapid series, i.e., "c²/h" = 1.36-50 * AMI at each Jewish Rosh Hashanah's (JRH's) two days' CHCF!) The "beauty" (or "elegance") of this new ("exciting") discovery of "G-D's Physics" ACC Paradigm – regarding its predicted (unique) "Critical Prediction" of an "UNCIARE-JRH's Accelerated Time Rate" is that it "ties together" (or "unifies") such an "UNCIARE-JRH's" AMI's (annual) increase – "simultaneously" pertaining to the Four basic Physical Features (e.g., of "space", "time", "energy" and "mass") as ensuing from the UCP "Universal Computational Formula", which has to be adjusted accordingly, accordingly:

Figure 4: The NEW "UNCIARE-JRH – AMI UCF"!

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{array} \right\} = \text{UNCIARE-JRH' AMI} * \left(\frac{s * e}{t * m} \right)$$

UF's {n...n...x} [Px| (a...z)]

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time". Wherein the UCP represented by the Hebrew Letter " , " computes at an extremely rapid rate, e.g., of "c²/h" = 1.36⁵⁰ (sec') simultaneously every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising every consecutive UF's – including the UCP's complete integration of those Four basic Physical Features through the UCF's: s * e / t * m computation (e.g., for each exhaustive spatial pixel – from "a to z")!

In order to compute the precise AMI (annual) increase brought about through this UCP's UCF – pertaining to each of those Four basic Physical Features, we must also take into consideration each of these Four Physical Features (specific new) UCP's Computational Definitions (accompanying the "UNCIARE-JRH – AMI UCF"):

The UCP's Four Physical Features (New) "Computational Definitions":

"Space"

S: $(f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$ such that: $f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] \leq f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}[UF's(i\dots n)]$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the.

"Energy"

E: $(f_{i\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$

such that: $f_{j\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)] > f_{i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}}[UF's(i\dots n)]$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes): $M: \sum[O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}}[UF(n)] = O_{i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}}\{UF(i\dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$ where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

"Mass"

M: $[O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - [O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"Time"

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

T: $\sum[O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}}[UF(n)] \neq O_{i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}}\{UF(i\dots n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$ such that: $T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - [O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

This means that this breakthrough discovery of "G-D's Physics" unique "UNCIARE-JRH's Time Acceleration" (Critical Prediction) could theoretically encompass and apply – not only to the (quantum) "Time-Acceleration"; and as explaining the "Hubble's Tension" (relativistic) "spatial" acceleration of the entire physical universe, but also to the other two basic Physical Features, i.e., of "mass" and "energy" – which are also predicted to increase by the same "UNCIARE-JRH's" UCP's AMI value at each consecutive JRH!

In other words, to the extent that this unique "UNCIARE-JRH – AMI UCF" "Critical Prediction/s" are empirically validated, i.e., (initially) through a measurement of: a) An "UNCIARE-JRH – AMI" Increase in rate of the universe's ("spatial") expansion rate (which begins during the upcoming JRH, e.g., Sep. 23rd -24th, 2025, relative to the current measured rate of the universe's expansion prior to these two JRH's special days of CHCF!) b) An "UNCIARE-JRH – AMI" Increase in rate of the universe's ("temporal") expansion rate (e.g., also beginning during those two days of the JRH's stipulated CHCF: at Sep. 23rd -24th, 2025, relative to the current measured "temporal" rate, prior to those two JRH's days!); and by extension – such (precise measurements) could be conducted pertaining the predicted "UNCIARE-JRH'S – AMI'S" increase in the measured vale/s of any universal phenomenon pertaining to its "energy" and "mass" value/s – also exhibiting a (UCP's) "UNCIARE-JRH – AMI" increase (beginning during the two days of JRH's Sep. 23rd -24th 2025)! Then, the empirical confirmation of such UNCIARE-JRH – AMI" Increase in the measurement/s of these (initial) two specified "Critical Predictions, i.e., pertaining the "UNCIARE-JRH – AMI" increase in: a) the universe's ("spatial") expansion rate; and b) it the universe's (fine) measured "temporal-rate" (e.g., as can be measured in any "atomic"- or "quantum"- "clock" or any fine-temporal measurement or even "sampling" of any physical process or phenomenon, see attached description in the "International Scientific Contest" all of these Four basic Physical Features could have quite "far-reaching" theoretical ramifications: First of all, it would differentially empirically validate "G-D's Physics" as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR's GRT & QM, thereby "crowing" "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-First Century's Physics Paradigm! Second, it would revise the MCR's current "Universal Time-Scaling" (see above discussion) as originating not in the MCR's (assumed) "Big-Bang" nuclear event (e.g., hypothesized to have occurred 13.8B years) – instead pointing at "G-D's Physics" centrality of the CHCF taking place during each consecutive JRH's two days UNCIARE's; with the stipulated AMI (empirical validation) indicating that the universe originated a mere 5785 years ago! Third, such empirical validation of these two (unique) "UNCIARE-JRH – AMI" "Critical Predictions" would also give a strong support for "G-D's Physics" "JRH's UNCIARE – AMI Universal Computational Formula", which unifies (for the first time in Physics) between those Four Physical Features within this singular UCF!

Obviously, such direct empirical support for "G-D's Physics" (candidate) NSP is strengthened by its (abovementioned) offering of alternative ("compelling") explanations for both GRT's "curvature of Space-Time", and QM's "Quantum-Entanglement" phenomenon – based on its (novel) "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, e.g., arising from the UCP's (singular higher-ordered "simultaneous") computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for every consecutive "Universal Frame"), which also fully integrates both GRT & QM as "special-cases" within "G-D's Physics" UCF!

In addition, "G-D's Physics" NSP opens new (and exciting) fields of study and additional (unique) "Critical Predictions" – which the empirical validation of even one of them would suffice to substantiate "G-D's Physics" as more valid than the (current) Old MCR Paradigm of GRT & QM, including:

A. The UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table"

"G-D's Physics" complete integration of both GRT & QM – as "special cases" within the broader theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) has also been (previously) shown to lead to the discovery of a (stipulated) "UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table", that could be derived from the different possible computational relationships for each of the "known" Standard Model's subatomic particles – as embedded within the UCP's "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), i.e., when we take into consideration the UCP's new "Computational Definitions" of each of these Four basic Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time")! Moreover, it is predicted by (this) "G-D's Physics" (novel) "UCF's Exhaustive Subatomic Particles' Computational Table", that any new (prospective) newly discovered subatomic "particle" or "element" could be derived based on this UCP's UCF and associated (novel) UCP's Computational Definitions of the Four Physical Features!

B. Precise Astronomical Measurement of the UNCIARE-JRH's Critical Prediction

Of an increase in the current Astronomical Value of the Universe's Expansion Rate, i.e., by a "Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc that will occur during the upcoming JRH: on Sep. 23rd -24th, 2025, e.g., relative to the currently measured rate of the universe's expansion prior to Sep. 23rd -24th, 2025 (with this increased MAI value expected to carry over through the entire next JRH, until the next JRH scheduled for Sep. 22nd & 23rd, 2026).

C. Longitudinal measurement of the (same) UNCIARE-JRH's cumulative MAI's – across any given time-span!

A second manner of testing (and validating) G-D's Physics UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction could be experimentally tested at particularly set "time-points", e.g., for instance: a) Before 10 years (e.g., 2014 after the JRH of 2014): a predicted 10 * MAI = 10 * MAI of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc "decrease" from the current Hubble's constant, i.e., ; b) Before 50 years (e.g., (e.g., 2014 after the JRH of 2014): a predicted 10 X MAI = 50 * MAI of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc decrease from the current Hubble's constant, c) Before 100 years : a predicted 100 X MAI = MAI of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc decrease from the current Hubble's constant.

D. "G-D's Physics Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances"

Regards a comparison of an Accelerator's precise measurements of the significantly greater number of times that such a ("more massive") Muon particle would appear across a given series of UF's frames (i.e., or in fact a certain measurable sample thereof!) than the "less-massive" electron particle! "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" (unique) "Critical Prediction", e.g., regarding the significantly smaller number of FTM's in which the 'electron' particle would be

detected relative to the number of (such) FTM's in which the 'Muon' may be measured – needs to be corrected for the known subatomic (quantum theory related) "bias" towards the measurement of such 'more-massive' 'Muon' particle, relative to the measurements of a 'less massive' 'electron' particle; In other words "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" "Critical Prediction" regarding the significantly greater FTM's at which the 'more massive' Muon particle (M) would be detected, relative to the number of (equivalent) FTM's at which the 'less-massive' electron (e) particle would be detected should subtract the "quantum measurement bias" (QMB) towards a more 'sensitive temporal measurement' of more massive particle:

$$\text{FTM}(M) - \text{QMB} > \text{FTM}(e)$$

To the extent that this "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" "Critical Prediction" is empirically validated, then this would provide an (unequivocal validation for "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm: i.e., specifically, for its novel conception of the manner in which that singular higher-ordered UCP differentially computes "more massive" particles, relative "less massive particles.

Hence, an "International Contest for Validation of "G-D's Physics" New Twenty-First Century's Scientific Paradigm's Further "Critical Predictions" (is hereby announced):

AN INTERNATIONAL CONTEST FOR VALIDATION OF G-D'S PHYSICS' NEW TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY'S PARADIGM'S FURTHER "CRITICAL PREDICTIONS"!

Background & Significance

Dr. Bentovish's (Bentwich) "G-D'S Physics" is being increasingly considered as the New Twenty-First Century Physics' Scientific Paradigm, i.e., with over 120 published (peer-reviewed) scientific articles; Indeed, two (unique) G-D's Physics' "Critical Predictions" have (recently) been empirically validated as more accurate than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, thereby "crowning" "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-First Century! One of these (two) empirical validations of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm pertains to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" ("UNCIARE") during the (stipulated) "Jewish Rosh-Hashanah's" (JRH's two days') "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) Critical Prediction points at the existence of a singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that (simultaneously) computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe at the incredible rate of "c²/h = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec(!) thereby allowing this singular UCP to produce an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" of the entire whole universe! In addition, this validated UNCIARE Critical Prediction indicates the existence of a (novel) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) theoretical postulate, which stipulates that whenever there exist such CHCF (of Millions of individual human-beings) on this singular UCP, then this brings about an increase in the UCP's rate of the universe's expansion!

Given the acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New Physics Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century, the Journal announces an "International Contest for Validation of 'G-D's Physics' New Twenty-First Century Paradigm's 'Critical Predictions'!" Astronomers, Cosmologists and Experimental Physicists are encouraged to submit articles describing their experimental validations of any of these specific "G-D's Physics" (unique) "Critical Predictions":

A. Precise Astronomical Measurement of the UNCIARE-JRH's Critical Prediction: of an increase in the current Astronomical Value of the Universe's Expansion Rate, i.e., by a "Minute Annual Increase" (MAI) of 0.000968 km s⁻¹ Mpc that will occur during the upcoming JRH: on Sep. 23rd -24th,

2025, e.g., relative to the currently measured rate of the universe's expansion prior to Sep. 23rd -24th, 2025 (with this increased MAI value expected to carry over through the entire next JRH, until the next JRH scheduled for (Sep. 12th & 13th, 2026).

B. Longitudinal measurement of the (same) UNCIARE-JRH's cumulative MAI's – across any given time-span! A second manner of testing (and validating) G-D's Physics UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction could be experimentally tested at particularly set "time-points", e.g., for instance: a) Before 10 years (e.g., 2014 after the JRH of 2014): a predicted $10 * MAI = 10 * MAI$ of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ "decrease" from the current Hubble's constant, i.e., ; b) Before 50 years (e.g., (e.g., 2014 after the JRH of 2014): a predicted $10 X MAI = 50 * MAI$ of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ decrease from the current Hubble's constant, c) Before 100 years : a predicted $100 X MAI = MAI$ of $0.000968 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}$ decrease from the current Hubble's constant.

C. "G-D's Physics Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances": regards a comparison of an Accelerator's precise measurements of the significantly greater number of times that such a ("more massive") Muon particle would appear across a given series of UF's frames(i.e., or in fact a certain measurable sample thereof!) than the "less-massive" electron particle!

"G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" (unique) "Critical Prediction", e.g., regarding the significantly smaller number of FTM's in which the 'electron' particle would be detected relative to the number of (such) FTM's in which the 'Muon' may be measured – needs to be corrected for the known subatomic (quantum theory related) "bias" towards the measurement of such 'more-massive' 'Muon' particle, relative to the measurements of a 'less massive' 'electron' particle; In other words "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" "Critical Prediction" regarding the significantly greater FTM's at which the 'more massive' Muon particle (M) would be detected, relative to the number of (equivalent) FTM's at which the 'less-massive' electron (e) particle would be detected should subtract the "quantum measurement bias" (QMB) towards a more 'sensitive temporal measurement' of more massive particle:

FTM(M) – QMB >FTM(e)

To the extent that this "G-D's Physics' Differential-Mass 'Fine-Temporal Measurements' (FTM) Appearances" "Critical Prediction" is empirically validated, then this would provide an (unequivocal validation for "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm: i.e., specifically, for its novel conception of the manner in which that singular higher-ordered UCP differentially computes "more massive" particles, relative "less massive particles.

D. "G-D's Physics" "UNCIARE-JRH – AMI" Universe's "Time-Acceleration": The "UNCIARE-JRH – AMI Universe's Time-Acceleration" (new) "Critical Prediction" predicts that based on the JRH's stipulated (two days of special) "CHCF", there occurs an AMI (equivalent) "acceleration" in the UCP's rate of "time" computation (for all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe!) This implies that if we measure – with (any) "Fine-Temporal Measurement/s" (FTM) precision (e.g., such as with "Atomic-(Optic) Clock/s", "Quantum Logic-Spectroscopy") of any physical phenomenon or process or rate, it is predicted that that FTM "Universe's Time Rate", i.e., rate of the universe's development (i.e., or of any subsystem physical system or phenomenon or process etc.) would "accelerate" itself (e.g., due to the UCP's UNCIARE-AMI increase in its rate of UF's computation/s!) beginning during the upcoming JRH, e.g., Sep. 23rd -24th, 2025, relative to the current measured rate of the "Universe's Time Rate" (e.g., as defined above)! rate of the universe's ("temporal") expansion rate (e.g., also beginning during those two days of the JRH's stipulated CHCF: at Sep. 23rd -24th, 2025, relative to the current measured "temporal" rate, prior to those two

JRH's days!); (*By extension, prospective FTM's could be made pertaining to the 'equivalent' "UNCIARE-JRH'S – AMI'S" increase in the measurement of the two other Physical Features of "energy" and "mass" value/s for any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, e.g., or any physical phenomenon or object/s or Physical System etc. – beginning during the two days of JRH's Sep. 23rd -24th 2025, relative to before those two JRH's days!)

Dedication

This profound article (and International Contest Announcement) is dedicated to the Lubavitcher Rabbi, to HAARI-ZAL (Rabbi Yitzchak Lurya Ashkenazy), Maimonides, HaBaal Shem Tuv, my dear beloved (diseased) Mother, Dr. Tirzah Bentwich (Tirzah Bat Yitzchak), my children, Shoham, Nethanel Yossef & Neomy Tirzah Shulamit, and my dear beloved wife, Shulamit Bentovish.

Scientific Contest Committee

The selection of the Five Winning Articles will be carried out by a Scientific Contest Committee, Chaired by Dr. Jehonathan Bentovish who is the "Father" of this New "G-D's Physics" Twenty-First Century's Scientific Paradigm.

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